

E-COMIC PEMBELAJARAN PENGOLAHAN SAMPAH BERORIENTASI STEM-MEA BAGI SISWA SEKOLAH MENENGAH

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Abstrak

Tujuan penelitian untuk menghasilkan sebuah media berupa *e-comic* pembelajaran pengolahan sampah berorientasi STEM (*Science, Tehnology, Engineering, and Math*)-MEA (*Means-End Analysis*). Metode penelitian yang digunakan adalah *research and development* dengan model 4D (*Define, Design, Develop, dan Disseminate*). Tahap *define* dilakukan *analysis* kebutuhan terhadap media; tahap *design* dengan cara membuat narasi secara manual, *storyboard*, dan pembuatan komik digital menggunakan program aplikasi; tahap *develop* dengan cara melakukan uji produk ke ahli media dan ahli materi serta mengujicobakan produk ke siswa Sekolah Menengah Pertama (SMP) Negeri 12 Padang; tahap *disseminate* dengan melakukan publikasi. Sampel penelitian berjumlah 42 siswa kelas VII. Instrumen penelitian menggunakan angket validitas dan praktikalitas. Teknik analisis data menggunakan analisis deskriptif dengan persentase kevalidan dan kepraktisan. Hasil penelitian memenuhi kriteria sangat valid dan praktis sehingga *e-comic* layak digunakan untuk pembelajaran mengenai pengolahan sampah.

Kata Kunci: *e-comic*; media pembelajaran; STEM-MEA.

Abstract

The research aimed to produce media in the form of e-comic learning about STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Math)-MEA (Means-End Analysis) oriented waste management. The research method used research and development with a 4D model (Define, Design, Develop, and Disseminate). The define stage was carried out by analyzing the needs of the media; the design stage by manually creating narratives, storyboards, and making digital comics using an application program; the developing stage by conducting product tests to media experts and material experts as well as testing the product on State Junior High School (SMP) 12 Padang students; disseminate stage by publishing. The research sample was 42 students from class VII. The research instrument used a validity and practicality questionnaire. The data analysis technique used descriptive analysis with validity and practicality percentages. The results of the research meet the very valid and practical criteria so that e-comics are appropriate for use in learning about waste management.

Keywords: *e-comic*; learning media; STEM-MEA.